

Kinetics and Mechanism of CO Substitution of $M_2(CO)_{10}$ ($M=Mn, Re$) with an Entering Ligand (PPh_3 or Py) in the Presence of an O-Atom Transfer Reagent (Me_3NO or $(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$)

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Detailed kinetic data are reported for the CO substitution of $M_2(CO)_{10}$ ($M=Mn, Re$) with PPh_3 or Py in the presence of Me_3NO or $(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$ as an O atom transfer reagent in $CHCl_3$ solvent. The rates of reactions are first order in concentrations of $M_2(CO)_{10}$ and of oxides but zero order in entering ligand concentrations. The reactions of $M_2(CO)_{10}$ with N -oxide are faster than for the corresponding reactions with Te oxide. Although the compound $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ reacts at about the same rate as does $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ in the presence of N -oxide, the manganese compound reacts 28 times faster than does the rhenium compound in the presence of Te -oxide. The results obtained are discussed in terms of the presumed mechanism of reaction.

Hieber and Lipp¹ first reported the use of pyridine N -oxide to facilitate CO release from $Fe(CO)_5$. A decade later, Alper and Edward² established the generality of the reaction and suggested a possible mechanism. Since that time such reactions have played an important role in organometallic chemistry, particularly in the syntheses of metal carbonyl derivatives³.

In spite of the extensive applications made of these reactions, the first detailed kinetic study of the reaction was only reported⁴ in 1987. The reaction mechanism seems to involve attack of an O-atom transfer reagent on a CO of the metal carbonyl. This results in the conversion of a good ligand CO into a poor ligand CO_2 , which then is a good leaving group and its departure affords a coordinatively unsaturated metal. The extremely reactive open coordination site will then rapidly react with solvent⁵ and/or added entering ligand⁴.

Kinetic studies of O-atom transfer have been made on molecular binary metal carbonyls⁴ such as $M(CO)_6$ ($M=Cr, Mo, W$), and on metal carbonyl clusters⁶ such as $M_3(CO)_{12}$ ($M=Fe, Ru, Os$). It was observed that for the triad of molecular compounds the rates of reaction increase in the order $Cr < Mo < W$, whereas for the triad of cluster compounds the rates vary in the opposite order of $Fe > Ru > Os$. The increase in reactivity of the Cr molecular triad was attributed to steric factors, an increase in rate correlating an increase in size of the metal. The decrease in reactivity of the Fe cluster triad was said to result from the decreasing tendency to form bridging COs, which are more effective in delocalising the increased electron density of the system caused by the nucleophilic attack.

In an attempt to better understand the presumed effect on rates of reaction due to steric factors versus CO bridging, it was decided to investigate the simplest of 'clusters' $M_2(CO)_{10}$ ($M=Mn, Re$). Reported here are kinetic data on the O-atom transfer reaction (equation 1),

$M_2(CO)_{10} + R_nE-O \rightarrow M_2(CO)_9 + CO_2 + R_nE$ (1)
($M=Mn, Re$; $R_nE-O=Me_3NO, (CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$)
of $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ with two different O-atom transfer reagents.

Results and Discussion

Rates of the reactions (equations 2 and 3),

($M=Mn, Re$)

of $M_2(CO)_{10}$ in $CHCl_3$ solvent with entering ligand in the presence of Me_3NO (equation 2) and of $(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2Te$ (equation 3) were monitored by changes in ir and uv-visible absorption spectra with time, respectively. Spectral changes for all the reaction mixtures show good isobestic points (Figs. 1 and 2), which suggest good stoichiometric reactions. This was confirmed by the fact that the ir-spectra of all reaction products in the CO stretching region were in good agreement with reported⁷ spectra for the known compounds. Plots of k_{obs} vs O-atom transfer reagent (i.e. N -oxide or Te -oxide) concentrations show a first order dependence on [oxide] (Figs. 3 and 4). That the rates

Fig. 1. Ir absorbance change of ν_{CO} vs time for the reaction, $Re_2(CO)_{10} + (p-CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO + Py \rightarrow Re_2(CO)_8Py + (p-CH_3OC_6H_4)_2Te + CO_2$.

Fig. 2. UV-vis absorbance change vs time for the reaction, $Re_2(CO)_{10} + Me_3NO + PPh_3 \rightarrow Re_2(CO)_8PPh_3 + Me_3N + CO_2$.

Fig. 3. Plot of k_{obs} vs $(p-CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$ concentration for the reaction $Re_2(CO)_{10} + (p-CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO + Py \rightarrow Re_2(CO)_8Py + CO_2 + (p-CH_3OC_6H_4)_2Te$.

of reactions are zero order in entering ligand concentration is shown in Table 1. Thus, CO substitution obeys the second order rate law given by equation (4).

$$-d[M_2(CO)_{10}]/dt = k_2[M_2(CO)_{10}][oxide] \quad (4)$$

Second order rate constants and activation parameters for the reactions (equations 2 and 3) are included in Table 2. Relative rates between the two reactions and relative basicities between the two oxides are given in Table 3.

Fig. 4 Plot of k_{obs} vs Me_3NO concentration for the reaction, $Mn_2(CO)_{10} + Me_3NO + PPh_3 \rightarrow Mn_2(CO)_9PPh_3 + CO_2 + Me_3N$.

TABLE 1—OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR REACTIONS OF EQUATION (2) WITH CHANGES IN PPh_3 CONCENTRATION AT A FIXED Me_3NO CONCENTRATION IN $CHCl_3$ AT 30.5°

M	$[PPh_3] \times 10^3 M$	$[Me_3NO] \times 10^3 M$	$k_{obs} \times 10^4 s^{-1}$
Mn	5.64	2.28	1.20
	5.58		1.16
	8.46		1.08
	9.40		1.16
	11.28		1.11
Re	1.89	1.82	0.586
	3.79		0.575
	5.63		0.571
	7.59		0.525

The reactions of $M_2(CO)_{10}$ ($M=Mn, Re$) with entering ligand ($L=PPh_3, Py$) in the presence of Me_3NO and of $(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$ afford the mono-substituted complexes $M_2(CO)_9L$ (equations 2 and 3). The rates of disappearance of $M_2(CO)_{10}$ follow a second order rate law (equation 4), first order in

TABLE 2—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR REACTIONS OF EQUATION (2) AND EQUATION (3) RESPECTIVELY

M	L	T °C	k_2 $M^{-1} S^{-1}$	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Mn	PPh ₃	23.4	2.7×10^{-1}	16.7 ± 1.4	-5.46 ± 0.45
		30.5	4.9×10^{-1}		
		37.3	1.06		
		44.0	1.73		
Re	PPh ₃	23.4	1.7×10^{-1}	16.4 ± 0.84	-6.82 ± 0.26
		30.5	3.2×10^{-1}		
		37.3	5.8×10^{-1}		
		44.0	1.11		
Mn	Py	18.0	6.40×10^{-2}	16.2 ± 0.8	-12.9 ± 0.2
		24.0	1.07×10^{-1}		
		39.7	5.10×10^{-2}		
Re	Py	21.0	3.23×10^{-2}	20.4 ± 3.6	-5.50 ± 0.5
		30.5	7.44×10^{-2}		
		37.1	2.04×10^{-2}		

$M_2(CO)_{10}$ and in O-atom transfer reagent concentrations but zero order in L concentrations (Table 1). This rate law and kinetic behaviour are the same as those reported earlier^{4,6,8} for the corresponding reactions of mononuclear metal carbonyls and metal clusters. Thus, the same mechanism is proposed (Scheme 1).

($M=Mn, Re$; $R_nE-O=Me_3NO, (CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$; $L=PPh_3, Py$)

Scheme 1

This associative mechanism is further supported by the activation parameters for the reactions, which are low values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and negative values of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (Table 2).

TABLE 3—RELATIVE RATES OF O-ATOM TRANSFER BY THE REAGENTS Me_3NO AND $(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$ TO $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ AND TO $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ IN $CHCl_3$

Compd.	$Me_3NO-PPh_3$ (23.4°)	$(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO-Py$ (24°)	Reactivities of N- and of Te-oxide	Relative basicity* $\Delta\nu_{OH}$ (cm ⁻¹)
$Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ (2012 cm ⁻¹)	0.272 ($M^{-1} s^{-1}$)	1.07×10^{-3} ($M^{-1} s^{-1}$)	$Me_3NO >$ $(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$ $\sim 25 : 1$	$Me_3NO >$ $(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$ $\sim 400 : 800^a$
$Re_2(CO)_{10}$ (2012 cm ⁻¹)	0.172 ($M^{-1} s^{-1}$)	3.84×10^{-4} ($M^{-1} s^{-1}$)	$Me_3NO >$ $(CH_3OC_6H_4)_2TeO$ $\sim 450 : 1$	
Relative rates	$Mn_2(CO)_{10} >$ $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ 1.6 : 1	$Mn_2(CO)_{10} >$ $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ 28 : 1		

*Ref. 18.

One reason for choosing to investigate the two compounds $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ and $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ is that they have identical structures, with a single M—M bond and no bridging COs. Another reason is that their CO stretching frequencies have approximately the same ν_{CO} values in $CHCl_3$ of 2 046 (s), 2 012 (vs) and 1 982 (m) cm^{-1} for $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$; 1 972 (s), 2 012 (vs) and 1 982 (m) cm^{-1} for $Re_2(CO)_{10}$. These similar values of ν_{CO} suggest that the C-atoms in the two compounds have similar charges, and they should respond to nucleophilic attack on CO based on the ground state at about the same rate⁹ for both clusters. This is in accord with what is observed experimentally (Table 3), that the rates of reaction of $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ and of $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ are about the same ($Mn_2 : Re_2 = 1.6 : 1.0$).

In spite of this correlation of rates of reaction with the ground state values of ν_{CO} , it is known⁴ that for the molecular carbonyls $M(CO)_n$ such a correlation does not exist. For these molecular compounds, the ν_{CO} values decrease in the order $Cr \sim Mo > W$ but the rates of reaction increase in the order $Cr < Mo < W$. The result was attributed to steric effects on the stabilities of the transition states for reaction, destabilising for the smaller Cr atom relative to the larger W atom.

Just the opposite result was obtained⁶ for the iron triad of carbonyl clusters $M_3(CO)_{12}$ (Fe, Ru, Os), where the rates of reaction with Me_3NO decrease in the order $Fe > Ru > Os$. This is contrary to the increasing sizes of the metal atoms and to the increasing ν_{CO} values of the carbonyl clusters. Again the relative rates are attributed to the stabilities of the transition states, which are believed to be stabilised by the formation of bridging COs known¹⁰ to be more effective in delocalising electron density on the metals resulting from nucleophilic attack. Evidence abounds¹¹ that the ease of CO bridge formation decreases in the order $Fe > Ru > Os$, in accord with the decreasing order of the reaction rates of these $M_3(CO)_{12}$ clusters.

Fortunately, there is significant information on CO bridging relevant to the system in this study. Photochemical and matrix isolation studies¹²⁻¹⁴ show that the species $M_2(CO)_9$ have the structures represented in equations (5) and (6).

It is uncertain if the CO bridge (equation 5) is of the classical type shown or if it is a semibrige

to the discussion here. The important point being that the active intermediates (or transition states) in Scheme 1 can be represented by structures (I) and (II).

With this background information and assuming that steric factors and CO bridging play an important role in stabilising the transition state, it is possible to offer a rationale for the rates of reaction of $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ and of $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ with Me_3NO being about the same. Simply put, the larger size of Re relative to Mn would sterically stabilise the transition state for reactions causing $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ to react faster. However, its inability to form a CO bridge would not permit it to electronically stabilise the transition state relative to the bridging Mn_2 system, resulting in a slower reaction. Providing the steric acceleration due to the larger Re and the electronic acceleration due to Mn_2 bridging each contribute about equally to the reaction rates, then the observed rates of reaction of the two carbonyls should be about the same. This, in fact, is what is observed experimentally.

Although the reactions of Me_3NO with $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ and with $Re_2(CO)_{10}$ proceed at about the same rate, their reactions with $(CH_3OC_6H_4)TeO$ differ in rate ($Mn_2 : Re_2 = 28 : 1$). It appears that for this O-atom transfer reagent, steric acceleration due to the larger Re is less important than is the electronic acceleration due to the bridging Mn_2 system. Why should this be, since the two effects for the O-atom transfer reagent Me_3NO are about the same? The answer may be the difference between having Me_3NO or $(CH_3OC_6H_4)TeO$ in the transition state for reaction. One important difference is perhaps the electronegativities of N (3.07) and of Te (2.01). Considering that the driving force for CO bridging in the transition state is to assist delocalisation of the increased electron density on a metal atom, it follows that there would be less electron density to delocalise in the more electronegative N containing (Me_3NO) system than in the less electronegative Te system. This would have no effect on $Re_2(CO)_{10}$, which perhaps does not form CO bridges but only has a more favorable steric rate acceleration because of its larger size than Mn. However, if CO bridging is important in the rates of reaction of $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ with the O-atom transfer reagents N—O and Te—O, then the driving force for reaction is expected to be larger for the Te than the N transition state because Te is less electronegative than N and would allow a larger electron density on Mn. The net result is that CO bridging becomes relatively more important in the TeO reactions, and since only $Mn_2(CO)_{10}$ can take advantage

of this, its reaction becomes 28-times faster than that of $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$.

The above rationale is based on the assumption that $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ does not form a CO bridge in its transition state (II), because matrix isolation of $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_9$ is known¹²⁻¹⁴ not to contain a CO bridge. However, whether or not CO bridges form in clusters is often controlled by the delicate balance of the ligand basicities on the metals. For example, only Co and Rh in the clusters $\text{M}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ (M=Co, Rh, Ir) have CO bridges, but all three of the metals have bridging COs in $\text{M}_4(\text{CO})_{11}\text{PR}_3$ ¹⁵⁻¹⁷ where one of the π -acid CO ligands is replaced by a more basic PR_3 ligand. It then follows that the transition state for the reaction of $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ may contain a CO bridge as does $\text{Mn}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ (I), providing the O-atom transfer reagent is a sufficiently strong base to put enough electron density into the system to cause CO bridging. Since the base strength of Me_3NO is stronger than that of $(\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{TeO}$ (Table 3), it may be that the basicity of Me_3NO causes CO bridging even in the reaction of $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$. Thus the combined rate enhancement of the Re_2 system because of its larger size and its CO bridge formation may just offset the greater tendency of the Mn_2 system to form a CO bridge in the transition state. In such a case, if the compensating effects are about the same, the rates of reaction would be similar as is experimentally observed. In contrast to this, if the base strength of $(\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{TeO}$ is not sufficient to cause CO bridging in the transition state of the $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ reaction, this driving force for reaction is not available to it but is available to $\text{Mn}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$. It then follows that the steric rate acceleration of $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ may not be enough to overcome the electronic rate acceleration of the CO bridge formation of $\text{Mn}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$. If this happens the net result is that the relative rates of reaction would be $\text{Mn}_2(\text{CO})_{10} > \text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ which is consistent with the experimental results.

Experimental

Manipulations involving the dinuclear metal carbonyls $\text{M}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ (M=Mn, Re) were routinely carried out under a N_2 -atmosphere by using standard Schlenk techniques. Chloroform was purified and dried by published¹⁹ procedures. The solvent which was generally spectroscopic grade, was distilled under a N_2 -atmosphere prior to use. The metal complexes $\text{M}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ were obtained from Strem Chemicals. Trimethylamine *N*-oxide (Me_3NO) was obtained either as the dihydrate (Aldrich) and purified by sublimation or it was synthesised by a literature method²⁰. $(p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{TeO}$ was synthesised and purified by the literature method²¹. The nucleophile PPh_3 was purified by recrystallisation from anhydrous ethanol. Pyridine (Strem) was distilled over CaH_2 in a N_2 -atmosphere prior to use.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Nicolet-SDX FT-IR using 0.5 mm NaCl cells or on a

Nicolet 5PC-FT-IR using 0.2 mm NaCl cells and ultraviolet-visible spectra on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells.

Kinetic measurements: Rate data for the disappearance of reactant metal complexes were obtained by monitoring uv-vis spectral changes and by monitoring spectral changes in the ν_{CO} region of the ir. All the reactions were performed under pseudo-first order conditions with the concentration of O-atom transfer reagent and of ligand being at least 15-times greater than that of $\text{M}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$. In a typical experiment using the ir spectrophotometer, a solution of $(\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{TeO}$ and Py was prepared in a flask, and the flask was placed in a temperature-regulated jacket. Constant temperature ($\pm 0.2^\circ$) was maintained by an external circulating bath (Neslab RTE-8). After 15 min of temperature equilibration, a CHCl_3 stock solution of $\text{M}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ was syringed into the flask. After the flask was vigorously shaken, an aliquot was removed by syringe, the aliquot was syringed into an ir cell flushed with N_2 and sealed with rubber septa, and the resultant spectral changes were monitored.

Plots of $-\ln A$ vs time for the disappearance of reactant and plots of $-\ln(A_\infty - A)$ vs time for the appearance of product were linear over two half-lives (linear correlation coefficient > 0.995). The slopes of these lines yielded k_{obs} . Both methods for monitoring the reaction rates yielded similar k_{obs} values for a given reaction.

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